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Analysis of the effectiveness of the discriminant function in solving the problem of country classification based on a set of indicators

KEYWORDS

discriminant analysis,
country classification,
within-group correlation,
discriminant constant

ABSTRACT

Introduction. The relevance of studying discriminant analysis in solving economic problems is due to its ability to improve decision-making, forecasting, risk management, and adaptation to changes. In a dynamic and competitive economic environment, this method becomes an important tool for analyzing and optimizing various business processes.

The study is aimed at investigating the comparative effectiveness of the method for constructing a discriminant function in solving the problem of classifying countries based on a set of indicators.

Materials and methods. Publications in peer-reviewed journals on economics, statistics, and data analytics were used, as well as materials from conferences dedicated to new approaches in discriminant analysis. Methods included theoretical literature analysis, modeling for forecasting and classification. The research task involved analyzing seven macroeconomic indicators of 25 countries (data from open sources). The goal was to identify key features, study internal discrimination, and construct a linear hyperplane for classifying countries based on these features.

Results. The results of country classification using discriminant analysis are presented. Factors determining country discrimination were identified. The weight and significance of each studied macroeconomic indicator in discrimination were analyzed. The discriminant function and discriminant constant were determined, allowing the group of countries to be divided into two classes, each with its own within-group correlation distribution. New objects were classified using the constructed discriminant function.

Conclusion. Discriminant functions were constructed to classify countries based on seven macroeconomic indicators, taking into account their weight and significance. Differences in within-group correlation allow countries to be divided into two classes. Key factors identified include GDP, exports, imports, foreign direct investment, and population size. The results demonstrate high model robustness. In the context of technological development and Big Data, discriminant analysis can be enhanced through machine learning and AI, expanding its application in finance, marketing, healthcare, and other fields.

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INTRODUCTION

The relevance of the study stems from the fact that, with the advancement of technologies and the increasing volume of available data, discriminant analysis has become more accessible and applicable. Modern software tools enable rapid and efficient processing of large datasets, making this analysis increasingly pertinent.

Discriminant analysis allows for the effective classification of objects (e.g., companies, products, customers) based on their characteristics. This is particularly important in economics, where accurate decision-making can significantly impact financial outcomes and competitiveness. Methods of discriminant analysis aid in forecasting various economic phenomena, such as the probability of borrower default, the market success of new products, or consumer behavior. This enables companies and organizations to plan their actions more precisely and minimize risks.

Amid uncertainty and instability in financial markets, discriminant analysis serves as a critical tool for risk assessment and management. It facilitates the identification of high-risk groups and supports the implementation of measures to mitigate such risks.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Discriminant analysis is employed for bankruptcy prediction as it enables the classification of companies into “bankrupt” and “non-bankrupt” categories based on a set of features (financial indicators). It constructs a discriminant function that maximally separates these groups, and the function's value determines the probability of bankruptcy. This method aids in the timely identification of risks and the implementation of measures to prevent financial problems.

K. Kočíšová and M. Mišanková describe predictive models, i.e., those capable of assessing a company's financial health and alerting company owners and business partners before the threat of bankruptcy arises. The authors additionally examine discriminant analysis [1].

S. Ben Jabeur et al. note that one of the primary objectives of bankruptcy prediction is to determine the model specification with the strongest explanatory power. The authors propose an enhanced XGBoost algorithm, which is compared with seven machine learning algorithms based on three well-known feature selection methods commonly used in bankruptcy prediction: stepwise discriminant analysis, stepwise logistic regression, and partial least squares discriminant analysis [2].

N. A. Rashid et al. compare the capabilities of partial least squares discriminant analysis in classifying bankrupt firms with the benchmark logit model [3].

Ligang Zhou describes the development of corporate bankruptcy prediction models. The effectiveness of these models depends on several processes, such as sampling, feature selection, modeling, and evaluation criteria. In order to achieve models with better predictive performance, numerous quantitative methods have been utilized, including discriminant analysis [4].

T. Kliestik et al., implementing multiple discriminant analysis, identify the most significant predictor and the best discriminants of corporate well-being, as well as forecasting models for individual V4 countries and a comprehensive model for the Visegrad Group. The predictive models use a combination of the same financial ratios to forecast a company's future financial development [5].

Discriminant analysis is applied to identify factors influencing population poverty and to classify groups by wealth level. It helps to identify characteristics that distinguish the poor from the non-poor and to predict the likelihood of an individual or region falling into a low-income group, thereby facilitating the development of targeted social support measures.

R. Georgescu et al. explore a quantitative approach to the determinants of the Human Development Index (HDI), specifically GDP per capita, the Gini net income index, the Gini wealth index, and the poverty rate. The authors employ multiple discriminant analysis to predict four classes of the HDI [6].

Y. Issahaku et al. evaluate a discriminant function model to analyze demand-side barriers to financial inclusion in Northern Ghana. The authors conclude that the majority of vulnerable groups in Northern Ghana continue to face difficulties in accessing formal financial services due to barriers such as culture, cost, accessibility, and trust [7].

D. H. Nasution et al. note that in Indonesia, particularly in North Sumatra, poverty remains a central issue. In order to identify the factors that most significantly influence and differentiate the poverty levels of districts/cities in North Sumatra, a discriminant analysis method is used. Through discriminant analysis, the authors identify the unemployment rate as a factor influencing poverty [8].

L. Pavić et al. state that discriminant analysis is a useful tool for predicting potential demand in Serbian motels. The authors extract 14 dimensions of potential guest expectations [9].

Sh. Singh et al. use Fisher's linear discriminant analysis to classify 100 randomly selected households into four farming groups, namely: rice, rice-fish, rice-vegetable, and others. Important discriminant variables include farm income, agricultural land, number of workers, agricultural assets, income from services, other income, etc. [10].

A. Csikosova et al. note that the complex system of stone quarries, gravel and sand pits necessitated the application of discriminant analysis to evaluate individual settlements with the aim of categorizing them into profitable and non-profitable locations. The authors classify quarrying settlements into profitable and non-profitable categories, serving to predict the future development of the company based on discriminant analysis [11].

M. Egbo and D. Bartholomew conduct a discriminant function analysis to classify 68 randomly selected countries according to their respective economic status using data from the World Bank website. The following economic indicators were used as independent variables: gross domestic product, mortality rate, inflation rate, and access to electricity [12].

Thus, discriminant analysis is currently one of the widely used types of analysis, employed to classify, rank, differentiate, and categorize large volumes of data. The task of discrimination, as a classification problem, holds significant importance in the study of macroeconomic processes. The relevance of the topic is driven by the increasing complexity of such processes. The volume of data under study is growing, classification conditions are changing, and the number of qualitative variables used to describe processes is increasing. In order to enhance the efficiency of such analysis, modern information technologies and specialized application software packages are utilized.

This study is aimed at investigating the comparative effectiveness of the method for constructing a discriminant function in solving the problem of classifying countries based on a specific set of indicators.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The research materials included studies published in peer-reviewed scientific journals on economics, statistics, and data analytics, which describe the application of discriminant analysis in various economic contexts.

Additionally, materials from conferences on statistics, economics, and data analytics were used, where new approaches and research results in the field of discriminant analysis are discussed.

Research methods include theoretical analysis (study and analysis of existing literature on discriminant analysis, its methodology, and application in economics), modeling (developing models based on discriminant analysis for forecasting and classification), data analysis (using software tools for data analysis and interpretation of results).

Problem statement

The study was conducted on selected macroeconomic indicators of a group of countries (see Table 1), consisting of 25 states. The data include seven macroeconomic characteristics and were obtained from open access sources [13]. The objectives were to identify the most significant features, examine discrimination within the studied population, and construct a linear hyperplane for country classification.

Table 1

Selected countries and macroeconomic indicators

Countries	Macroeconomic indicators	Designations
Australia, United Kingdom, Hungary, Vietnam, Germany, India, Iraq, Iran, Spain, Italy, China, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Russia, Romania, Singapore, USA, Turkey, Finland, Croatia, Sweden, Switzerland, South Korea, Japan	GDP per capita (USD)	X_1
	Volume of exported goods in 2021 (million USD)	X_2
	Volume of imported goods in 2021 (million USD)	X_3
	Inflation rate in 2021 (%)	X_4
	Population in 2021 (million people)	X_5
	Labor productivity (thousand RUB)	X_6
	Foreign direct investment, FDI (% of GDP)	X_7

RESULTS

According to the United Nations ranking of world economies in 2021-2022, the top 15 countries from our list include the USA, China, Japan, Germany, the United Kingdom, India, Italy, Russia, South Korea, Australia, and Spain [14]. These countries will be considered as Class A, while all others (excluding Poland and Vietnam) will be classified as Class B. This constitutes the analyzed sample. The two separately identified countries (Poland and Vietnam) are assigned to the validation sample.

During the discriminant analysis, mean and active values for each group were calculated (see Table 2).

Table 2

Mean values of macroeconomic indicators for Classes A and B

Mean values	GDP per capita (USD)	Volume of exported goods in 2021 (million USD)	Volume of imported goods in 2021 (million USD)	Inflation rate in 2021 (%)	Population in 2021 (million)	Labor productivity (thousand RUB)	FDI (% of GDP)
Class A	40124.5	25.5	23.4	4.3	236.9	7.6	40.1
Class B	44873.5	73.1	53.0	7.1	42.9	8.0	31.1

The mean values of macroeconomic indicators for the classes do not allow for an unambiguous discrimination of the entire dataset.

The within-group correlation matrices for the two groups differ significantly from each other (see Table 3).

Table 3

Within-group correlation matrices

Factors	X ₁	X ₂	X ₃	X ₄	X ₅	X ₆	X ₇
Class A							
X ₁	1						
X ₂	0.152	1					
X ₃	0.186	0.973	1				
X ₄	0.356	0.069	0.055	1			
X ₅	-0.423	-0.392	-0.446	-0.341	1		
X ₆	-0.226	-0.235	-0.117	-0.271	0.234	1	
X ₇	0.619	0.027	0.119	0.178	-0.289	0.564	1
Class B							
X ₁	1						
X ₂	0.553	1					
X ₃	0.681	0.504	1				
X ₄	-0.339	-0.185	-0.234	1			
X ₅	-0.475	-0.539	-0.435	0.416	1		
X ₆	0.373	0.401	0.007	0.003	-0.199	1	
X ₇	0.439	-0.042	0.099	-0.287	-0.250	0.198	1

No multicollinearity is observed in Class B, unlike in Class A. The variables of export and import volumes demonstrate a noticeable (according to the Chaddock scale) correlation with GDP per capita in Class B, and a very weak correlation in Class A

(see Table 4). In Class A, correlation with GDP is only notable with the FDI factor, while in Class B, it is only moderate. The only very strong correlation is observed between export and import volumes in Class A, whereas in Class B, export volume shows only a noticeable correlation with both import volume and population size. Additionally, labor productivity and investments are noticeably correlated in Class A. The remaining correlations are insignificant.

Based on the structure of the correlation matrices, it can be concluded that the factors determining the classification of countries are GDP, export volume, import volume, FDI, and population size.

Table 4

Distribution of correlation strength among factors by Class affiliation

Significant factor	Classes	Correlation strength by Chaddock Scale			
		Weak and very weak (0-0.3)	Moderate (0.3-0.5)	Noticeable (0.5-0.7)	High and very high (0.7-1.0)
GDP per capita	Class A	Export, import, labor productivity	Inflation rate, population	FDI	
	Class B		Inflation rate, population, productivity, FDI	Export, import,	
Export volume	Class A	GDP, inflation rate, labor productivity, FDI	Population		Import
	Class B	Inflation rate, FDI	Labor productivity	GDP, import, population	
Labor productivity	Class A	GDP, export, import, inflation rate, population		FDI	
	Class B	Import, inflation rate, population, FDI	GDP, export		

The study employed a forced inclusion procedure for all variables. Covariance matrices for each Class SA and SB were determined, followed by the calculation of an unbiased estimate of the pooled covariance matrix:

$$M = \frac{1}{n_1 + n_2 - 2} (S_A + S_B)$$

After obtaining the inverse matrix of M (M^{-1}), the vector of discriminant function coefficient estimates was defined as:

$$D = M^{-1} (X_{Am} - X_{Bm})$$

Then the discriminant function takes the form:

$$D = 0,0006x_1 - 0,1843x_2 - 0,8308x_3 - 1,0785x_4 + 0,0282x_5 - 1,8668x_6 - 0,0743x_7$$

The values of the discriminant function were computed for each country. The mean values for clusters A and B were determined, and the discrimination constant was calculated as the arithmetic mean of the discriminant function estimates for Class A and Class B:

$$D_0 = \frac{1}{2} (D(X_A)_m + D(X_B)_m)$$

Table 5

Mean values of the discriminant function
for classes A and B and the discrimination constant

$D(X_A)_m$	$D(X_B)_m$	D_0
0.395	-52.784	-26.194

All objects satisfy the constructed classification with the exception of Norway and Finland (see Table 6). The values of the discriminant function for these countries (-13.1 and -19.7) according to the constructed discrimination belong to Class A.

Table 6

Values of the discriminant function for each country

Class A	China	India	Great Britain	Spain	Russia	Italy
	32.5	-12.8	-8.9	-8.5	-10.9	-3.8
	Australia	USA	South Korea	Japan	Germany	
	7.3	24.3	-16.5	11.0	-9.3	
Class B	Singapore	Sweden	Switzerland	Norway	Netherlands	Hungary
	-107.4	-66.5	-41.3	-13.1	-49.9	-72.5
	Romania	Finland	Iraq	Iran	Croatia	Turkey
	-50.7	-19.7	-50.4	-70.1	-51.8	-39.9

Let us reassign these two countries, adjust the obtained classes, and analyze their correlation matrices (see Table 7).

The distribution of within-group correlation has changed: a strong linear relationship is now observed in group B as well, with import and GDP showing close correlation. The significance of imports has increased for both Class A and Class B.

Table 7

Within-group correlation matrices
(the lower triangular matrix corresponds to Class A,
the upper triangular matrix corresponds to Class B)

	X1	X2	X3	X4	X5	X6	X7
X1	1	0.663	0.802	-0.311	-0.678	0.354	0.423
X2	0.266	1	0.466	-0.260	-0.589	0.458	-0.015
X3	0.350	0.965	1	-0.312	-0.459	0.033	0.134
X4	0.235	-0.038	-0.085	1	0.505	0.002	-0.281
X5	-0.439	-0.427	-0.473	-0.267	1	-0.415	-0.369
X6	-0.121	-0.190	-0.057	-0.243	0.212	1	0.172
X7	0.601	0.027	0.115	0.204	-0.274	0.582	1

The indicators of export and import exhibit noticeable and strong correlation with GDP in Class B, and weak (or moderate) correlation in Class A (see Table 8). In Class A, the correlation of GDP is only noticeable with the FDI factor, while in Class B, it is only moderate. Export volume demonstrates a moderate relationship with population size and a strong relationship with imports in Class A, whereas in Class B, a moderate correlation is observed with labor productivity and imports, and a noticeable correlation with GDP and population size. In Class A, labor productivity is primarily (and noticeably) influenced by FDI, while in Class B, it is moderately influenced by three factors simultaneously: population size, GDP, and export. The remaining correlations are insignificant.

It should be noted that the set of factors determining the classification remained unchanged after the reassignment of countries.

Table 8

Distribution of correlation strength among factors by Class affiliation

Significant factor	Classes	Correlation strength by Chaddock Scale			
		Weak and very weak (0-0.3)	Moderate (0.3-0.5)	Noticeable (0.5-0.7)	High and very high (0.7-1.0)
GDP per capita	Class A	Export, inflation rate, labor productivity	Import, population	FDI	
	Class B		Inflation rate, population, labor productivity, FDI	Export	Import
Export volume	Class A	GDP, inflation rate, labor productivity, FDI	Population		Import
	Class B	Inflation rate, FDI	Labor productivity, import	GDP, population	

Labor productivity	Class A	GDP, export, import, inflation rate, population		FDI	
	Class B	Import, inflation rate, FDI	Population, GDP, export		

The maximum absolute correlation value of each factor with others characterizes the weight coefficient of that factor in the discriminant function (see Table 9).

Table 9

Weight of macroeconomic indicators in the classification

GDP	Export	Import	Inflation rate	Population	Labor productivity	FDI
0.80	0.97	0.80	0.51	0.68	0.46	0.60

Let us calculate the covariance matrices for each class, determine the unbiased estimate of the pooled covariance matrix, and recalculate the discriminant function:

$$D = 0,0020x_1 - 0,5339x_2 - 1,6209x_3 - 2,3316x_4 + 0,0341x_5 + 0,3408x_6 - 0,3934x_7$$

The discriminant multipliers have changed, some significantly. For example, the multiplier for x_4 has more than doubled, and the multiplier for x_6 has changed sign and become substantial. The discrimination constant has shifted leftward along the axis (see Table 10).

Table 10

Mean values of the discriminant function for groups A and B and the discrimination constant

$D(X_A)_m$	$D(X_B)_m$	D_0
15.565	-77.664	-31.049

Now all objects satisfy the constructed classification. The values of the discriminant function for objects in Class A lie to the right of the discrimination constant D_0 , while those for Class B lie to the left (see Table 11), indicating the robustness of the discrimination process.

Table 11

Values of the discriminant function for each country

Class A	China	India	Great Britain	Spain	Russia
	42.889	-30.014	-6.020	-4.993	-14.013
	Italy	Australia	USA	South Korea	Japan
	14.633	39.862	74.177	-15.465	40.805
	Germany	Norway	Finland		
	4.520	39.494	16.471		
Class B	Singapore	Sweden	Switzerland	Netherlands	Hungary
	-129.295	-92.416	-47.804	-38.384	-123.258
	Romania	Iraq	Iran	Croatia	Turkey
	-71.753	-70.311	-107.841	-53.800	-41.776

Classification of new objects by discriminant functions. The test sample consists of two objects – Vietnam and Poland, the values of the discriminant function for them are as follows:

$$D(V) = -203.428D(P) = 66.582$$

According to the constructed classes, both Vietnam and Poland belong to Class B, which is consistent with logical reasoning and confirms the acceptability of the linear hyperplane D.

The task of classifying an arbitrary group of objects (countries) is inherently challenging [15]. When defining a specific class, it is essential to account for the characteristics of the objects under study, including the large number of variables and parameters used to describe their state; their interdependent and dynamic correlations;

frequent high noise levels in variable measurements; missing data; presence of outliers in measurements; inclusion of qualitative variables; uncertainty in object behavior. These and other factors significantly complicate the classification process. The decision to introduce a new class remains highly subjective.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Discriminant functions were constructed to classify countries based on seven selected indicators. The weight and significance of each macroeconomic factor in the discrimination process were determined. Differences in the distribution of within-group correlation enabled the classification of countries into two distinct classes. In

this study, the factors that defined the discrimination of countries were GDP, export volume, import volume, FDI, and population size.

Variations in the set of discrimination variables, the prioritization – hierarchy of factors – or other defining conditions for classification will characterize different discriminant functions and differences in class determination. The results of testing the constructed discriminant function demonstrate a high degree of robustness.

Thus, given the rapid development of technologies and data analysis methods, discriminant analysis can be adapted and enhanced using new approaches such as machine learning and artificial intelligence. This opens up possibilities for developing more complex and accurate models capable of effectively addressing economic challenges.

With the increasing availability of big data and advanced processing technologies, discriminant analysis can be applied to analyze complex and multidimensional datasets. It can be utilized across various economic sectors, including finance, marketing, insurance, healthcare, and others. This creates opportunities for interdisciplinary research and practical application of the method in new contexts.

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